

USE OF THE INTERNET FOR READING: A CASE STUDY OF PUNJABI UNIVERSITY, PATIALA

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ABSTRACT

The advent of computers and the Information communication Technologies (ICT) has revolutionized the way of access and use of information. It has even brought a great change in information storage, handling and retrieval. The entire universe has converged into a global village. The libraries which are the highly trusted and a valued resources are also undergoing transitions from traditional to hybrid, hybrid to digital and digital to virtual libraries. With this changing scenario, library users as well as their information needs are also changing. The informed citizenry has resulted in an informed and cautious users who are well aware of their information needs. The reading style and habits are also changing in this tech savvy era. Those days are gone when users used to depend on their physical visits to the libraries. The digital and virtual libraries have brought the entire information at their computer/laptop/mobile's screen. The emergence of electronic publishing has revolutionised the information seeking activities of the end users. Young users are relying more on electronic resources to quench their information thirst. Technological revolution has resulted in saving the precious and valuable time of the users, solving the storage problem and facilitates the information sharing and transfer.

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1. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Ureigho, Oroke and Ekruyota (2006) evaluated the impact of the Internet for learning, teaching and research in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The study revealed that students and staff use Internet mainly for on-line chatting (24.89%) and e-mail (24.16%). The use of Internet as a source of research materials ranked third (23.21%). This study concludes that research would significantly improve through proper enlightenment, formal training on the use of Internet and provision of effective Internet services in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Nwagwu et al. (2008) revealed that younger users (<24 years) and older colleagues (>24 years) use chat rooms. About 73 per cent of the respondents considers internet information as useful while much less than this (44.4 per cent) reported finding internet information as trustworthy.

Maharana, Sethi and Behera (2010) studied the necessity and usage of Internet and e-resources by the students undertaking the master's course in Business Administration, in Sambalpur University, Orissa, India. The study gives an indication of the range of uses of internet and e-resources by MBA students. The investigation result shows that majority of the students (1/3 of them) have a long experience of using Internet for 2 - 4 years and all are more or less aware of the applications of Internet technology. More than half of the students surveyed in the study strongly feel that management study will be severely affected without the use of internet and e-resources.

Brar's (2012) study deals with information seeking behavior of Ph.D researchers. The author conducted a survey to reveal the use of library, various techniques of consulting library services and their purpose. E-resources and e-journals acceptance and awareness is also analyzed. The study also exposes the problems faced by researcher and their satisfaction level.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study was carried out with the following objectives:

- To explore the use of the Internet.
- To identify the purpose of the Internet use.
- To reveal the favourite search engine of the users.
- To find out the problem faced by users while online searching.
- To identify the preference of format while online reading.
- To study the satisfaction level of users

3. SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study deals with the Use of Internet for reading by students of Punjabi University, Patiala. Interestingly, Punjabi University, Patiala (India) is the second university of the world to be named after language subsequent to the Hebrew University of Israel. Majority of the students obtaining admission to various courses being offered by this university are from rural areas. The university campus spreads over 600 acres of land and has a faculty of 500 teachers imparting instructions and guidance to more than 10,000 students in a multi-faceted, multi-pronged and multi-faculty environment comprising 65 Teaching and Research Departments on its Campus.

To achieve the objectives of the study, a structured questionnaire was prepared to collect the data from the students, related to various disciplines. The questionnaire contained relevant questions pertaining to use of the Internet. For this purpose a total of 85 questionnaires were distributed among students. Out of those 85 questionnaires, 80 valid questionnaires were

collected and then data was analyzed, tabulated, interpreted and graphically represented in this paper.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1 Sample of the Study

Category of users	Number of Users	Percentage
Postgraduate	50	62.5
Researchers	30	37.5
Total	80	100

The table 1 shows the category of users. There are total 80 students for this study. Out of the 80 students, 50 students were pursuing master degree and the remaining 30 were Students of M. Phil. or Ph. D degree.

5. PURPOSE OF USING INTERNET

The study revealed the majority of students (66.25%) use the Internet for educational purpose, only 26.25% for entertainment and few (6.25%) for playing online games. A very few (1.25%) students use it for other purpose which includes chat, shopping, etc.

6. FREQUENCY OF USE

As far as frequency of using the Internet is concerned, majority of users i.e. 88.75% access it daily as with the advent of ICT, easy and cheap availability of the infrastructure. Most of the students have the basic Internet access equipments i.e. Computers, laptops, note pads, Tabs, Smart Phones, etc. The university's entire campus has the Wi-Fi Internet connectivity. Only ten percent users access the Internet 2-3 times in a week, while 1.25% students use it occasionally.

Figure 1

7. LOCATION OF ACCESSING THE INTERNET

The figure depicts the location of accessing the Internet. Most of the students (47.50%) access it from their hostels or homes, 26.25 access it from the department and 20% access the Internet from the university library. Internet cafe and other places are used by 2.5% and 3.75% users respectively.

8. DEVICES USED FOR THE INTERNET ACCESS

The users were asked about the device through which they access the Internet. It was interesting to find that as many as 53.75% students use their mobile phones to access the Internet. The reason behind is the modern mobiles are fully advanced with having Wi-Fi connectivity, word editor, e-reader, and other facilities. Thirty five percent students use their laptops, 7.5% students use tablet computers while the remaining 3.75% are using the personal computers.

9. SOURCE USED FOR ACQUIRING INFORMATION

Source of information acquisition is most important in the present era of information explosion. There are lots of chaos and superabundance of unauthentic and unreliable information on the Internet. The study depicts that majority of users (65%) find the useful information through search engines. 26.25% students access the desired information directly from the web addresses (URLs) provided by their teachers, seniors and friends. Online library catalogues and subject directories are used by 6.25% and 2.5% students respectively.

10. PREFERRED SEARCH ENGINE

The students are asked about their frequently used search engine. Google is the most popular search engine among the students which is used by 85% students. Yahoo search engine is used by 11.25% students. The remaining 3.75% students use the other search engines like Cuil, Altavista, etc.

11. PROBLEMS FACED DURING SEARCHING

The users are enquired about the problems faced during online searching. The study expressed that 51.25% students do not know the important websites of valuable information in their subjects, while 31.25% and 17.5% respectively expressed that they are faced with irrelevant information and information overload on their subjects.

12. CRITERIA FOR JUDGING THE RELEVANCE OF INFORMATION

The first attribute of information is relevance. The study exposed that majority of students 66.25% use title of the paper to evaluating its relevance. The author's name and position is used by 15% students. 10% use the domain name from where they are getting information to check the relevance. Remaining 8.75% rely on descriptors to ascertain significance of the information.

13. FORMAT PREFERENCE IN ONLINE READING

Further, it was asked from the students to ascertain that what format of information display they prefer. In response, 58.75 per cent of the respondents confirm that they prefer HTML format, while the PDF format has been confirmed as preferred by 26.25 per cent of respondents. In addition, only 15 per cent respondents have given their preference to the other formats like DOC or image format.

14. TIME SPENT ON ONLINE READING IN A WEEK

In response to the query that how much time the students spent on online reading

Time Spend	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Up to 2 hours	18	22.5
2-5 Hours	39	48.75
More than 5 Hours	23	28.75
Total	80	100

in a week. 48.75 percent students spend 2-5 hours on reading the information online. More than 5 hours are spent by 28.75 per cent students. Remaining, 22.5 per cent respondents have confirmed to spend up to 2 hours on online reading in a week.

15. SATISFACTION LEVEL OF THE USERS

It was asked from the students that whether they were satisfied from the information available online. Positively, 77.50 per cent of the respondents expressed their complete satisfaction to the online availability of information, while the 21.25 per cent appeared partially satisfied and only 1.25 per cent respondents are not satisfied.

16. FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

The ICT has made a profound impact on all the aspects of the society. LICs as well as the readers/users are no exception to it. It was interesting to found that all the respondents of the present study are IT savvy and are using the Internet extensively for education, research, reading, leisure and entertainment. Most of the users frequently uses the Internet and are using their hostels, homes, departments, university library as locations for the Internet usage. The advent of mobile technology with high specifications and enhanced features has resulted in making the mobile phones a popular device for the Internet usage. The search engines especially the Google is extensively used for accessing information. The title of the document still remains an important criterion for judging the relevancy of the information. The HTML format is the most preferred format for online reading. The users are satisfied by the services offered by the Internet but problems like information overload and excess of irrelevant results are posing hindrance to a number of users.

It is recommended that the users should be given short term training and lectures to train them in the evaluation of information for relevancy, currency, authenticity, authority and reliability. The university libraries are in a very good position to impart this type of training to the end users. The teaching faculty should coordinate with the library staff. The teachers should help users in finding maximum reliable information by suggesting important and relevant URLs related to the coursework.

In essence it can be said that though the ICT has revolutionised the information access, transfer and usage process and as the e-publishing industry is gaining momentum, the print and the online formats will coexist. The electronic format is only an enhancement and not a replacement of the print format.

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